

QUALITY SUPERVISION IN TECHNOLOGY AND VOCATIONAL EDUCATION: A CATHOLICON FOR SUSTAINABLE NATIONAL DEVELOPMENT

¹Bala Anthony Gora, ²Giwa Musibau ³Osakue E. Felicia & ⁴Briska Sulisari Solomon

^{1,2,3} Department of Building Technology Education School of Secondary Education (Technical). Federal College of Education (Technical) Asaba Delta state.

Tel: ¹07088884557, ²08032897082, ³07061206435, ⁴07068728744

Email: ¹balaagora@gmail.com ²musbaugiwa@gmail.com, ³eloagunu2016@gmail.com, ⁴sulisarib@gmail.com

Abstract

This paper examined the relevance of quality supervision in Technology and Vocational Education (TVE) as a Catholicon for sustainable National Deployment. Specifically, this paper examined the concept of Technology and Vocational Education and its relevance to economic growth and sustainable national development. The study also attempts to highlight the significance of quality supervision in Technology and Vocational Education programme to include; contributing to the development of educational policies, providing regular feedback on performances, enforcing proper utilization of human and material resources, identifying and proffering solutions to the problems bedeviling the TVE programme, helping in creating and maintaining a positive and inclusive learning environment, and improving learning experiences for students. Characteristics and the purpose supervision in TVE were also highlighted. Challenges facing quality supervision in Technology and Vocational Education programme were identified, while Solutions to the challenges were proffered. It was concluded among others that, all concerned authorities should ensure that the challenges rocking the smooth implementation of

quality supervision in TVE programmes must be fully addressed, supervisors should be motivated through adequate remuneration for additional responsibilities.

Keywords: Sustainable Development, Technology and Vocational Education, Quality Supervision.

Introduction

Maintaining and improving the quality of human capital resources, economic growth, and sustainable development of any nation depends on the quality of its Technical and Vocational Education (TVE). Technical and Vocational Education (TVE) according to FGN (2013) is "A comprehensive term referring to those aspects of the educational process involving, in addition to general education, the study of technologies and related sciences and the acquisition of practical skills, attitudes, understanding, and knowledge relating to occupations in various sectors of economic and social life". This definition emphasises the integration of theoretical knowledge and practical skills to equip individuals for productive work and lifelong learning in both formal and informal sectors of the Nigerian economy and beyond.

This implies that TVE holds the key to training the skilled and entrepreneurial workforce needed for the changing technological advancement and economic challenges. It is the type of education that centered on the acquisition of knowledge, attitude, and practical skills for the world of work in order to improve opportunities for productive empowerment and socio-economic development in knowledge of economics and rapidly changing work environment (Byiyet, 2023).

Thus, TVE equips individuals not only with technical skills, but also with a wide range of knowledge, attitude and other related practical skills that are relevant and indispensable for meaningful participation in work and social life. Therefore, the improvement of Technical and Vocational Education programme requires quality supervision.

The importance of supervision in any programme be it private or public cannot be over-emphasized, and with quality supervision of any establishment, results and improvement becomes possible and development is attainable. From the aforementioned, it is clear that, quality supervision will improve the quality of the programme in Nigeria by pinpointing the administrative responsibilities of the day-to-day operation of the programme. It could also ensure that departments, administrators, teachers and instructors are doing their jobs for the benefits of the students (Benaiah, 2022). Gwazayet, (2020) pointed out that, the provision and establishment of TVE programme in Nigeria does not just occur without putting in place adequate measures to ensure the realization of its fundamental objectives. Hence, supervision is an essential control element or a fundamental pillar that ensures the maximum achievement of the goals and objectives of the TVE programme.

Therefore, the improvement of Technical and Vocational Education programme in Nigeria requires quality supervision, because supervision is an indispensable control mechanism in the implementation and improvement of any programme in effort to ensure the achievement of its intended purpose.

The Meaning and Concept of Supervision

The concept of supervision has not enjoyed a universally acceptable definition, as many scholars, professionals and practitioners with different epistemic understandings at different point in time tend to define the term based on their intellectual insight at the moment, or based on the purpose it is to be applied. According to Gwazayet, (2024) etymologically, the term supervision is derived from two Latin words “super” (above) and “videre” (see/observe). Eziuzo, (2021) sees supervision as the act of providing leadership through a process designed to help staff gain greater competence and overcome some barriers so as to improve job performance.

Akilaiya, (2023) opined that supervision is the act or way of advising, guiding, refreshing, encouraging, stimulating, improving and overseeing certain groups with the hope of persuading people to desist from applying wrong procedures in carrying out certain functions on their jobs and trying to emphasize the importance of good human relations in an organization. It is a relationship among human beings to perform the task efficiently and effectively to improve process of instruction. In the context of this paper, supervision is the process of stimulating growth and a means of helping teachers to help themselves. It is an instrument for the quality control system of Technical and Vocational Education programme. Thus, supervision should be purposeful, related to the democratic norms and total system of the TVE programme, because it creates leadership qualities in teachers, respect individual differences, help individual teachers in diagnosing of teaching difficulties and recognises the inherent importance of an individual teacher.

From the foregoing, it is evident that supervision concerns the general observation of available human and material resources in a selected programme or school as a model by some designated educationists to see if things generally are going as expected, and if not to give advice, guidance, encouragement and ideas on the ways for the improvement of teaching and learning. Hence, the importance of supervision in TVE programme today demands for greater attention because people are becoming more conscious now than in the past about the importance of TVE programme.

Purpose of Supervision in Technology and Vocational Education

There are numerous reasons for supervising TVE programme, but particularly, the primary objective of supervising the programme according Geri, (2020), is to enhance quality of the TVE by ensuring conformity to the basic standards of operation of the academic and non-academic components of the programme. It is also to ensure the creation and maintenance of conducive atmosphere for teaching and learning to thrive, which will result to productivity in the TVE programme and the society at large. Geri further outlines the purpose of quality supervision in TVE to include;

- ❖ **Promote Spirit of Professionalism in Teachers:** Supervision of TVE programme is aimed at ensuring that teachers/instructors imbibe the spirit of professionalism to jobs by working effectively and efficiently to enhance the productivity and the quality of TVE.
- ❖ **Encourage Regular Training and Re-training:** It is a well-known fact that professional supervisors seek to discover skills, talents as well as appraise the instructional competences of the teachers, after ascertaining their capabilities and weaknesses, the supervisor then recommends to

- ❖ the management the training need for each teacher/staff through conferences, in-service training, refresher courses, seminars, workshops, among others to ensure that they are abreast with current trends in their career.
- ❖ **Discovering Teachers' Abilities:** Supervision exercises if not for anything helps the supervisors to discover the capacity of various teachers. This helps the supervisors to provide technical and professional advice to the management on the training needs, placement, promotion, and general job description for each teacher/staff.
- ❖ **Improvement of Teacher/Staff Morale:** Improving the morale of TVE teachers/staff is one of the essential purposes for supervising the TVE programme. This is because, many teachers/staff sometimes loss focus of their job and or are not motivated to putting their best in the job because of some challenges, therefore, the purpose of supervision is to encourage and motivate them to be enthusiastic about their job, thereby, improving their overall job performance.
- ❖ **Provision of Technical Help to Teachers:** Providing technical help to TVE teachers is one of the reasons supervisors are expected to be senior, experienced and more knowledgeable than the teachers for the purpose of providing technical assistance to teachers and the management in the areas of teaching and learning difficulties, instructional material preparation, improvisation and utilization of modern/new instructional techniques, innovations in teaching among other things.
- ❖ **Guide Teachers in the Use of Modern Instructional Material:** Supervision of TVE programme is designed to help teachers to be more resourceful in the choice, preparation and utilization of the

most suitable instructional materials and Information Communication Technology (ICT) to facilitate effective learning process in the classroom.

- ❖ **Recommendation for Grants and Loans:** Quality supervision of TVE programme leads to the recommendation for grants in aid either from international organizations, private bodies or voluntary agencies.
- ❖ **Provision of Feedback to Educational Planners and Policy Makers:** If an educational planner designed a technical training institution for a certain number of learners, but few years later, the influx of the learners exceeds the carrying capacity of the institution's structure, it is through quality supervision that the planner will know that there is need for review and extension of such technical training institution.
- ❖ **Ensure Efficiency and Effectiveness in Fund Utilization:** Supervision of TVE programme helps to ensure that funds meant for TVE training institutions are effectively and efficiently utilized for the attainment of the goal and objectives of the TVE programme.
- ❖ **To Determine the General Well-being of the TVE Programme:** Quality supervision of TVE helps identify the disciplinary, financial or the learning problem/difficulties confronting the TVE programme.
- ❖ **To Determine the Cost and Benefit of the TVE Programme:** Technical and Vocational Education is one of the most effective educational programme in Nigeria, and it involves huge expenditure. Therefore, some aspects of modern/quality supervision focus on cost and benefit analysis of the TVE programme so as to save the government or private individuals from running into complete fiasco or humiliating situation in the operation of the TVE training institutions.

Characteristics of TVE Supervision

Osburn (2021) outlined the following characteristics of supervision in Technical and Vocational Education programme;

- ❖ **Cooperation:** All the parties/authorities concerned in the process, affairs and provision of TVE should offer suggestions and provide useful information and services to the supervisory administrative staff. In reality, supervisory activities should be in cooperation and not separate by the parties/authorities involved. Without maximum cooperation, the purpose of supervising the TVE programme will be defeated because it is expected that supervision is a process where all concerned parties/authorities unanimously make efforts to improve the teaching and learning practices in all TVE training institutions.
- ❖ **Integration:** Supervision has a motive of ensuring that all units/departments follow a singular/particular direction in the pursuit of one goal to avoid wastage of time, effort and resources in the achievement of the goal and objectives of the TVE programme. This implies that quality supervision of TVE programme seeks to harmonize the objectives and mission of various units and departments, streamlining them into central and overall objectives of the TVE programme.
- ❖ **Scientific:** Supervision of TVE programme should be specially structured and fully based on controlled teaching and learning process to ensure that the results offer suggestions to make a consistent readjustment with keen look at training more adopted and effective learners.
- ❖ **Flexibility:** Supervision of Technical and Vocational Education programme must be flexible and not rigid like the traditional inspection/supervision. Thus, it should be amendable to change and future adjustment.

- ❖ **Outstanding:** The action of Technical and Vocational Education supervision should not suffer interruption for whatever reason and not be permanent in the sense, and should also encourage those in the teaching and learning process.

Challenges of Quality Supervision in TVE

There are several challenges/problems which tend to militate against quality supervision of TVE programme in Nigeria. Mamsai, (2022) identified the following challenges:

- ❖ **Inadequacy of Personnel:** The quality of professionally trained supervisors is insufficient to meet the demand of an effective and efficient supervision programme. The number of trainers in the TVE programme, is beyond the teacher-trainee ratio to the point where most TVE administrators do nothing in terms of instructions. It is the responsibility of the instruction unit to guarantee that there are enough teachers/instructors to cover the classes.
- ❖ **Shortage of External Supervisors:** External supervisors are usually staff/officers of the Ministry of Education who are designated to assess the level of conformity of the instructional activities in all TVE training institutions with approved government standards. Unfortunately, due to enormous number of TVE training institutions and instructors, hence causing shortage of external supervisors to effectively carryout the supervisory activities as expected. The consequence of this shortage of quality supervisors is that supervision is being carried out by quacks (Ogunu, 2015).
- ❖ **Inadequate Instructional Materials:** Without instructional materials, there can be no effective delivery of instructions, however, experience has shown that most TVE training institutions lack even the most basic

instructional materials and equipment such as text books, chalk board, practical materials and equipment, adequate and conducive class rooms and environment for learning among others.

- ❖ **Inadequate Funds:** Insufficient or lack of funds often prevents supervisors from organizing in-house orientation and training programme for their teachers and instructors or travelling to other institution's resource centers to learn about new development, technology and instruction that could be of benefit to the TVE programme and the government.
- ❖ **Lack or Inadequate Training:** Many newly appointed/employed supervisors are not properly trained and also lack orientation that can equip them with the required skills to effectively carry out their instructional supervisory function, and as such, they manage or struggle for many years without understanding instructional or quality supervision is all about.
- ❖ **Time Constrain:** Majority of supervisors are overloaded with the routine of administrative activities so much that they hardly find time to visit the institutions in order to supervise the teachers/instructors, equipment and materials. Rather, these supervisors spend more time attending to correspondence with the education ministry, community affairs, parents, hence neglecting their primary function which is supervision. (Ogunu, 2015).

Significance of Supervision in TVE

Supervision in TVE is of numerous significance. Wiles and Levee (2015) in National Open University (2019) outlined the followings as the significance of supervision in any given organization or programme;

- ❖ **Goal Development:** One of the primary function of supervision is to guarantee that teachers/instructors and supervisors collaborates to achieve the organizational/institutional objectives. It is worth noting that the learning institution's objectives are derived from social objectives. Goal development as a function of

supervision is a continuous process that require constant investigation, evaluation, modification (if necessary), change or modifying the teaching-learning process through collaborative effort of both the teachers and the supervisors. Regularity of goal-development concern is a clear evidence of monitoring systems sensitivity and responsiveness to the dynamism of the societal goal.

❖ **Motivation:** Everyday, teachers and learners are confronted with a wide range of problems with various degrees of difficulties. These issues could be related to educational/organizational inputs, expected learning outcomes, curriculum programmes and actual learning. While the teachers may able to handle some of these issues on their own way, many others may take days to overcome and will require the supervisor's support. In all situations, the supervisory mechanism in place should be capable of resolving these issues as quickly as possible.

❖ **Professional Growth:** Teachers/instructors are expected to be experts in their fields. They are assumed to be educated, yet, the educational systems, as well as the society's expectations of the teachers are constantly changing. Teachers as stewards of the society's education, must adapt to reflect changes in technology, goal development, learning engagement and the learning environment of TVE training institutions. Teachers must be exposed to a continuous, comprehensive, and systematic programme of in-service training to enable them cope with these changes. It is the responsibility of the supervisors to initiate the support, coordinate and facilitate the implementations of the professional development programme for teachers and supervisors. As the educational system grew, more professional supervisors and teachers are needed.

❖ **Programme Development:** Teachers and instructors are primarily responsible for developing curricula and co-curricular activities. In this case, the supervisor's job is to provide appropriate supplementary technical and professional services and support. The programme is developed for teaching and learning

process at the level of either an educational sub-system, individual training institute or the classroom experiences. As a result, modification in these objectives is expected to lead to acceptable outcomes, while changes in the programme development are aided by supervisory system.

- ❖ **Control and Coordination:** TVE is a programme comprised of a number of interacting units and each unit has its own objective to meet while also contributing to the programme's broader objectives. It is a basic role of supervision to ensure that the various units are properly coordinated in order to develop the supervisory system and improve the quality of the TVE programme. On the other hand, effective coordination necessitates the establishment of a complete system of proper communication among the units.
- ❖ **Problem Solving:** In the entire TVE programme, teachers and learners are often confronted with different problems of varying degree. Majority of these problems may be related to inputs into the TVE programme, anticipated learning outcomes, curricula and co-curricular activities, and the actual learning. Some of these problems might be solved by the teacher/instructors immediately, while some which requires the intervention of the supervisor may take some days or weeks. Therefore, the supervisory unit should put in place a working system which is readily prepared to facilitate the resolution of emerging problems.
- ❖ **Evaluation of Educational Outcomes:** Evaluation is the act of examining the work, significance and the quality of a programme or a system in order to report to the appropriate authorities for prompt action. As such, evaluation in educational programme is worthless if the actual need is perceived beforehand and no action is taken to meet that particular need. Note that effective guidance cannot be provided in any educational system without quality evaluation.

Solutions to the Challenges of Supervision in TVE

Mamsai, (2022) proffered some possible solutions to the challenges facing quality supervision in Technical and Vocational Education programme, these include:

- ❖ **Joint Effort:** Supervision is not something done to the personality of employees, but rather, some collaborative activities in which both the supervisor and the supervisee has a critical role to play. Therefore, the supervisors and the supervisees should join effort together and work on the strategic plans such as defining of unit/department priorities, scheduling and allocating work, and coordinating, in order to jointly achieve the goal and objective of an organization or the educational programme.
- ❖ **Dual Focus:** Employees/staff must believe that they also have a significant role to play in selecting and defining the goal and objective of the programme, as well as developing strategies to achieve them. If the employees/staff believe that the goals and objectives of the programme are being imposed on them, they are less likely to make personal effort or investment in achieving them.
- ❖ **Knowledge and Information:** To effectively and efficiently accomplish their job obligations, employee/staff must comprehend what is expected of them. Understanding students' growth, current laws and other legal parameters of practices, trending technology, standards and institutional norms and regulations are all examples.
- ❖ **Work-Related Skills:** Supervisors must ensure that staff members are up to date on emerging trends in the field of students' development and that they are trained in an interpersonal communication, goal setting and computer skills. The skills must be refreshed on a regular basis for student affairs professionals to remain effective. Supervisors must also provide opportunities for member staff to grow and learn new skills.
- ❖

- ❖ **Attitudes:** Supervisors must instill positive attitudes in their staff. Individuals with positive attitudes are more likely to apply knowledge and skills in order to achieve the goal and objectives of the programme.
- ❖ **Personal Skills:** The synergic approach to supervision emphasizes a holistic approach to supervision. Similarly, consideration must be given to the development of personal skills and or work-related skills. Individuals must be encouraged to learn skills in order function effectively as professional.
- ❖ **Growth Orientation:** Career development of all staff is one of the major responsibilities of supervision. As supervisors are pursuing meaningful work that is personally satisfying them, they should ensure that assistance is provided to other staff members so that they can improve.
- ❖ **Clear Understanding:** It is essential that supervisors have a clear understanding of the adult theory of development so as to aid/better the development of staff at various stages of life. Someone who has been in the job for long might have personal or professional needs that are different from new staff. Therefore, these two individuals cannot be supervised in the same way.
- ❖ **Proactivity:** Supervisors usually focus on identifying problems instead of reacting to problems that are building over time. Supervision emphasizes on early identification of problems and developing strategies to lessen the effect or jointly prevent the problems by the supervisors and the staff. Therefore, staff should be free to seek advice or assistance from the supervisors, and the supervisors should not see it as weakness on their part.
- ❖ **Goal Based:** supervisors and staff are expected to have clear expectations of one another as supervision requires. Goals and expectations can be jointly developed where both parties make commitment to undergo regular review in order to determine the level of progress.

Conclusion

The effectiveness of any organization or programme depends on quality of supervision. Quality supervision in Technical and Vocational Education (TVE) aims at enforcing the implementation of TVE programme, contributing to the development of educational policies, providing regular feedback on performances, helping in the proper utilization of human and material resources, identifying and proffering solutions to the problems bedeviling the TVE programme, helping in creating and maintaining positive and inclusive learning environment leading to improving experiences for students.

It also shows that supervision in Technical and Vocational Education (TVE) is carried out for various purposes, ranging from promoting the spirit of professionalism in teachers/instructors/staff, enhancing the quality of Technical and Vocational Education programme, to creating and maintaining a conducive atmosphere for teaching and learning. It was also concluded that cooperative, integration, scientific, flexibility and outstanding were the characteristics of supervision, while inadequate personnel, instructional material, insufficiency of funds, lack of proper training, and inexperience supervisors among others are the challenges hindering the effectiveness of quality supervision in TVE programme. While joint effort, dual focus, knowledge and information, work-related and personal skills, clear understanding, growth orientation and positive attitudes among others were considered as solutions to the problems.

References

- Akiliaya, O. (2023), *Educational administration*. Freefa bag Investment Limited.
- Benaiah, S. G. (2020). *Vocational technical education in Nigeria*. Elsumme Educational Book Ltd.

- Byiyet, P. D. (2016). *Supervision and inspection in Nigeria educational system: Trends, Issues and Challenges*. Nigerian educational research association.
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2013) *National policy on education*. NERDC. Press
- Geri, J. A. (2015), *An introduction to foundation of education*. Rapid Educational Publishers Ltd.
- Gwazayet, A. (2020). *Modern supervision in education: Theory and practice*. London: Publication Ltd.
- Mamsai, F. (2022). *A handbook on school administration, planning and supervision*. Zedac educational research and publishing Ltd.
- National Open University of Nigeria (2019). Supervision of instructions, retrieved from www.nou.edu.ng/courseware on 18th /10/ 2024.
- Nworgu, J.I. (2015). *Educational research: Basic issues and methodology*. Enugu university trust publishers.
- Ogunu, J.I. (2018). *A guide to effective supervision of instruction in Nigerian schools*. Enugu: fourth dimension publishing Co.
- Uwaifo, V.O. (2014) Industrializing the Nigeria society through creative skill acquisition in vocational and technical education programme. *International journal of technical and vocational education* 4 (4), 142-145.